

IMPACT OF TYPHA GRASS ON FISH CATCH AND DISTRIBUTION IN GUMBE RIVER KEBBI STATE..

Y. A. Birnin-Yauri¹ M.L. Balarabe F. Daddy¹, Y. B. Ahmed² and Owotunse, S¹.

¹National Institute for Freshwater Fisheries Research, P.M.B. 6006, New Bussa, Niger State. ²Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, P.M.B. 1500, New Bussa, Niger State.

ABSTRACT:

The impact of Typha grass on fish catch composition of different water bodies in Kebbi State was studied. The experimental fishing was conducted, each water body was divided into A and B. A was open water while B Typha infested area. Five *Malian* traps was set in each area (A and B) for five consecutive fishing days respectively. The fish caught was identified, counted and measured (weight). The various parameters of the plant (Typha grass) was also measured and counted. The results on fish catch composition in terms of numbers and weight in open water was higher than Typha infested area in both dry and wet seasons.

KEYWORDS: Fish catch composition, weight in Typha grass area.

INTRODUCTION

Typha grass can be found in wetland sedges and meadows along moving streams, rivers banks and lake edges. The plant is found in areas of fluctuating water level such as road side ditches and reservoirs (Morton 1975). It is an erect perennial freshwater aquatic herb which can grow up to 3 or more meters in height. The leaves are thick ribbon like structure which has a spongy cross-section exhibiting air channels. The subterranean stem arises from thick creeping rhizomes. The flower structure is dense, fuzzy, cylindrical spike on the end of stem, with a gap 1-3 cm of naked stem between the upper, male portion (stamina) and lower, female (Pistillate) portion. Both male and female flower sections are roughly length. Male flowers lighter brown; female flowers, often green during bloom dark brown during maturation. Individual blossoms minute and closely on spike (Room 1980).

The surface of water cover by Typha grass prevent light penetration, excessive development of algae bloom also causing nuisance in cultivated fish ponds and small reservoirs. They even cause fish mortality due to oxygen depletion or release of extra-cellular metabolites which are toxic (Patnaik 1980).

According to (Bennett 1974) "There is evidence that dense stands of Typha grass may bind up nutrient materials throughout the growing season so that they are not available for production of phytoplankton and the organisms that feed upon phytoplankton" This means that although fish hatches would be large, the chances for larva survival would be greatly diminished. The objective of this research was to study the number of fish catch in two different locations. Typha infested and uninfested area so as to proffer some management control.

STUDY AREA

Kebbi State is located in the North West Zone of Nigeria. An undulating plain with altitude mainly between 350 and 680m above sea level. The area has one main basin, drained by Sokoto Rima rive. The vegetation ecology is distinguishable into the Northern Guinea and Sudan savannah. As result of human activities the trees were replace by shrubs from the South to the Northern boundaries. The area is wholly tropical with abundant solar radiation (400-500 wm^{-2}) incident mostly as beam radiation, 8 hours per day mean and minimum temperature is (17°C) and maximum (32°C) respectively

Kebbi has distinct dry and wet season. However they differ slightly in terms of latitude, longitude and amount of rainfall, Kebbi is located on latitude 12°28'N and long. 04° 11'E. Maximum rainfall range 305mm to 1048mm (National Agricultural Research Project, 1996).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in all water bodies in Kebbi State, where Typha was infested. Each river (water body) divided into two, A and B, A is open water while B is Typha infested area. Five *Malian* traps were set up in in each area for five days with dimension of 70cm diameter, 80cm height and 20 kg of baits. The number of fish catch and

weight in each area for two seasons were recorded. The plant height, length of leaves width of the leaves, length of inflorescent, the length of inflorescent tip was also measured, and number of tillers per plant was also counted. The data was analysed.

RESULTS

Table 1 and 2 shows the number of fish catch and there weight for five days in both A and B for the two season. The result shows increased catch during wet season in Area B Table 3 and 4 showed the morphological features of Typha grass during dry and wet season respectively while Figure 1 showed location A and B where the experiment was conducted.

Table 1: Number and weight of fish species caught in Area A and B during dry season for five days in Kebbi State

species	Area A Number	Weight(g)	Area B Number	Weight(g)
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	42	3710	—	—
<i>Bagrus bayad</i>	1	100	6	95
<i>Synodontis spp</i>	31	498	—	—
<i>Mormyrops spp</i>	10	920	—	—
<i>Hydrognus forskalii</i>	9	1700	—	—
<i>Malapterurus electricus</i>	6	134	—	—
<i>Heterotis niloticus</i>	2	780	6	141
<i>Lates niloticus</i>	2	145	—	—
<i>Clarias species</i>	7	2570	18	3650
ToTal	110	13,068	30	2,736

Table 2: Number and weight of fish species caught in Area A and B during wet season for five days in Kebbi State

species	Area A Number	Weight(g)	Area B Number	Weight(g)
<i>Hemichromis faciatus</i>	5	4500	—	—
<i>Hydrocynus forskalis</i>	15	1150	—	—
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	36	1442	8	180
<i>Bagrus bayad</i>	15	1040	9	978
<i>Clarias species</i>	15	1950	17	2400
<i>Lates niloticus</i>	7	6000	6	1350
<i>Malapterurus electricus</i>	4	1750	2	100
<i>Heterotis niloticus</i>	5	4500	9	539
<i>Synodontis species</i>	13	1900	5	1000
Total	115	24,232	56	7,662

Table 3: Morphological features of Typha grass during dry season in Kebbi States.

Plant height	2m	2.5m	2.8m	2.5m	2m
Length of leaf	2.1m	2m	1.8m	19m	2m
Width of leaf	0.5cm	0.4 cm	0.5 cm	0.8 cm	0.8cm
Length of inflorescent tip	22cm	31.0 cm	19.6 cm	25 cm	30cm
Length of inflorescent	42cm	90 cm	36 cm	39 cm	42cm
No. Of tiller	8	9	10		5

Table 4: Morphological features of Typha grass during wet season in Kebbi States.

pH	2.0m	2.5m	3m	1.5m	2m
length leaf	2m	1.75m	1.75m	2m	1.8m
width of leaf	0.5cm	0.8cm	0.5cm	0.5cm	0.5cm
Length of inflorescent tip	Non	Non	Non	Non	Non
Length of inflorescent	Non	Non	Non	Non	Non
No. of plant	8	6	5	2	5

Figure 1: A – un-infested by Typha grass in Kebbi State while B –infested by Typha grass in Kebbi State.

DISCUSSION

The result in Table 1 and 2 shows the fish catch and their weights during the two seasons in A and B. The data analysis showed significant difference in the catch. This may be associated with the facts that in B there is always lower catch because in Typha infested area there is low temperature, dissolve oxygen and light penetration. Therefore, few species of fish can survive in that area; Little (1979) reported that Typha decreased dissolve oxygen and lower temperature of the water, which alter the fauna living in water Cook (1976) also observed low temperature and radiation in Typha infested area only few species of fish can survive.

When data was analysed between A dry season and A wet season. It showed that there is no significant differences in catch. However there is a change in species and there weights. In B area during dry and wet seasons there is significant difference. This is as a result of increased in number of fish species catch during wet season. The may be associated with the fact that there is less population density of Typha grass during wet season. There is increase in dissolve oxygen and light penetration Patnaiki (1980) oxygen depletion cause low fish catch and fish mortality or release of extra-cellular metabolites which are toxic to fish.

There was higher turbidity which makes it difficult for the fish to identify the baits Prowse (1962). Observed High turbidity due to dense phytoplankton lower down catch even sometime lead to total migration of fish.

The height of the plant, width of leaves, and length of leaves numbers of tillers showed that there is no significant difference for the two seasons. However, the length of inflorescent and length of inflorescent tip showed significance difference for the two seasons. This is because of absence of inflorescent during wet season. Therefore, the population of plant was less dense; this could explain the reason why the catch was higher during wet season in B.

Some of the reasons associated with the higher fish catch in B Typha infested area during wet season because of changes in dissolve oxygen and improve in water turbidity fish turn to spawn in the area. This could also explain the reason why there was diversity of species in B during wet season. Cook (1976) observed that during wet season different species of fish migrate to higher dense aquatic environment. This may be due to season variation in temperature, dissolve and oxygen.

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Corresponding Author:

Y. A. Birnin-Yauri

National Institute for Freshwater Fisheries Research, P.M.B. 6006, New Bussa, Niger State.